

Functional and Radiological Outcomes of Posterior Lumbar Interbody Fusion in Patients with Degenerative Lumbar Spine Disease: A Prospective Observational Study

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12 May 2026
Accepted: 26 May 2026
Published Online: 8 June 2026

DOI:

Volume: 9, Number: 4, Page: 44-49

e-ISSN: 2789-5912
ISSN: 2617-0817

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ABSTRACT

Background: Degenerative lumbar spine disease (DLSD) is a major cause of chronic low back pain, disability, and poor quality of life in the world. Posterior lumbar interbody fusion (PLIF) is a popular surgical procedure used to stabilize the lumbar region in patients with degenerative diseases. The study aimed to evaluate the functional and radiological outcomes of PLIF in patients with degenerative lumbar spine disease in a tertiary care center in Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** This prospective observational study was conducted at National Institute of Traumatology and Orthopaedic Rehabilitation, Dhaka, Bangladesh, from January 2024 to June 2024. 40 patients with degenerative lumbar spine disease who received single- or two-level PLIF were recruited. The Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) of back and leg pain and the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) were used to measure functional outcomes preoperatively and at 3 and 6 months postoperatively. Radiological outcomes, including fusion status, implant position, disc height restoration, and lumbar lordosis, were assessed at 6 months. Data were entered and analyzed on SPSS version 26. **Results:** The majority (55%) of patients were male. The most common diagnosis was degenerative spondylolisthesis (45%), and the most frequently operated level was L4-L5 (62.5%). Significant improvements were observed in VAS back pain (7.8 to 2.1), VAS leg pain (7.2 to 1.9), and ODI score (58.4 to 22.6) at 6 months ($p < 0.001$). In 75% of patients, definite fusion was obtained, and in 95%, good implant positioning was obtained. Satisfactory overall outcomes (excellent + good) were achieved in 80% of patients. The complication rate was low, and no deaths were reported. **Conclusion:** PLIF is a safe and effective

surgical procedure for degenerative lumbar spine disease, offering significant improvement in functional status and acceptable radiological outcomes within 6 months of surgery.

Keywords: Posterior lumbar interbody fusion, Degenerative lumbar spine disease, functional outcome, Radiological outcome, Oswestry Disability Index

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INTRODUCTION

Degenerative lumbar spine disease (DLSD) is a spectrum of pathological conditions such as degenerative disc disease, lumbar canal stenosis, degenerative spondylolisthesis, and spinal instability. All these conditions are among the most important causes of chronic low back pain, functional disability, and reduced quality of life in the world [1]. The incidence of lumbar degenerative disorders is high, especially in low- and middle-income countries like Bangladesh, where manual labor and farming occupations predispose a large proportion of the working population to early-onset degenerative changes in the spinal column [2]. Surgery is recommended for patients with DLSD who do not respond to conservative management for a sufficient period. Among existing surgical procedures, posterior lumbar interbody fusion (PLIF) has become the gold standard for neural decompression and, at the same time, restoring segmental stability through 360-degree circumferential fusion [3]. Initially introduced by Cloward in 1952 and later refined with the introduction of modern cage implants and pedicle screw

instrumentation, PLIF provides direct access to the intervertebral disc, restores disc height, and corrects spinal alignment through a single posterior approach [4]. The functional outcomes of PLIF have been evaluated in a wide range of global populations using validated measures like the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) of pain and the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) of disability assessment. Several studies have shown that both back and leg pain scores have decreased significantly after PLIF, and that functional disability indices have improved [5]. Mobbs et al. conducted a systematic review that highlighted the effectiveness of interbody fusion techniques over posterolateral fusion alone in providing better pain relief and functional recovery in patients with degenerative spondylolisthesis and disc disease [6]. Radiological outcomes after PLIF, such as fusion rates, implant position, disc height restoration, and lumbar lordosis correction, are also important determinants of surgical success. The literature on fusion rates is widely varied, ranging from 70% to 95%, depending on the method of operation, patient selection, and the length of follow-up [7]. The association

between radiological fusion and clinical outcomes has been a subject of ongoing research, with some studies showing a positive correlation between solid fusion and improved functional scores [8]. Dural tears, wound infection, cage migration, and adjacent segment degeneration are well-documented complications following PLIF. Nevertheless, the incidence of major complications has decreased significantly over the last decade due to advances in surgical techniques, intraoperative neuromonitoring, and perioperative care [9]. Although there is increasing evidence in high-income countries, limited data exist on South Asian populations, including Bangladesh, especially regarding prospective follow-up of functional and radiological outcomes in a real-world clinical setting [10]. The study was therefore aimed at prospectively assessing the short-term functional and radiological outcomes of PLIF in patients with degenerative lumbar spine disease who were treated at a tertiary care neurosurgical center in Bangladesh.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This prospective observational study was carried out at National Institute of Traumatology and Orthopaedic Rehabilitation, Dhaka, Bangladesh from January 2024 to June 2024. A total of 40 patients diagnosed with degenerative lumbar spine disease who underwent posterior lumbar interbody fusion (PLIF) during the study period were enrolled using a purposive sampling technique. Patients aged 18 years and above with radiologically confirmed degenerative lumbar pathology, including degenerative spondylolisthesis, lumbar canal stenosis with instability, degenerative disc disease with instability, or recurrent disc prolapse with instability, who had failed at least 12 weeks of conservative management and consented to surgical intervention, were included in the study. Patients who had active spinal infection, malignancy, previous fusion surgery at the same level, severe osteoporosis, systemic

medical conditions, or who were contraindicated for major surgery were excluded. The main outcome variables were functional outcomes as assessed by the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) of back and leg pain and the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI), measured preoperatively and at 3 and 6 months postoperatively. Secondary outcome variables included radiological outcomes such as fusion status (graded as definite, probable, or non-fusion), implant position, disc height restoration, lumbar lordosis, and hardware-related complications, all assessed at the 6-month follow-up visit using plain X-rays and, where indicated, CT imaging. Prospective recording of operative parameters, including operative time, estimated blood loss, hospital stay, and mobilization timeline, was performed. The overall clinical outcome was rated on a four-point scale (excellent, good, fair, poor), and all perioperative and postoperative

complications were recorded. The data were entered into a structured data collection form and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Continuous variables were reported as mean and standard deviation, and categorical variables were reported as frequency and percentage. The paired t-test was used to compare pre- and post-operative functional scores, and p-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table I presents the demographic characteristics of the 40 participants in the study. The majority of patients were in the 41-50 years age group (35%), followed by 51-60 years (30%). The study group comprised 55% male patients, and 57.5% of participants were rural residents. Manual labor or farming (40%) was the most prevalent occupation.

Table I
Demographic Profile of the study population (n = 40).

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age group	18-40 years	8	20.0%
	41-50 years	14	35.0%
	51-60 years	12	30.0%
	>60 years	6	15.0%
Sex	Male	22	55.0%
	Female	18	45.0%
Residence	Urban	17	42.5%
	Rural	23	57.5%
Occupation	Manual worker/farmer/laborer	16	40.0%
	Service holder	10	25.0%
	Homemaker	9	22.5%
	Business / other	5	12.5%

Figure 1 Baseline Clinical Profile of the study population.

The preoperative clinical profile is illustrated in Figure 1. Low back pain was the chief complaint of all 40 patients (100%), and 85% had concomitant radicular leg pain. In 60% of cases, neurogenic claudication was present, and only 20% had motor weakness. The majority of patients (67.5%) had a symptom duration of more than 12 months, which means that they had a chronic disease course before surgery.

Significant comorbidities were hypertension (27.5%), diabetes (22.5%), and active smoking (32.5%), all of which could be potential modifiers of surgical outcome.

Table II shows the details of the radiological diagnoses and levels operated. The most common surgical indication was degenerative spondylolisthesis with

instability (45%), then lumbar canal stenosis with instability (30%). The most commonly operated segment was the L4-L5 level (62.5%). Most patients had single-level PLIF, with only 7.5% undergoing a two-level procedure, indicating the predominantly focal nature of the disease in this cohort.

Table II
Radiological Diagnosis and Operated Level of the study population.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Radiological diagnosis	Degenerative spondylolisthesis	18	45.0%
	Lumbar canal stenosis with instability	12	30.0%
	Degenerative disc disease with instability	7	17.5%
	Recurrent disc prolapses with instability	3	7.5%
Operated level	L3-L4	4	10.0%
	L4-L5	25	62.5%
	L5-S1	8	20.0%
	Two-level PLIF	3	7.5%

Table III describes the intraoperative and perioperative parameters. The average operative time was 154.8 ± 28.6 minutes, and the estimated blood loss was 420 ± 135 ml. The mean length of stay was 6.4 ± 1.8 days, and 85% of patients were mobilized within 48 hours of surgery, indicating an effective early recovery protocol. In 25% of patients, blood transfusion was necessary, most probably due to increased intraoperative hemorrhage in two-level or technically complex cases.

Table III
Operative and Hospital Profile of the study population.

Variable	Category	Mean ± SD / n (%)
Operative time	-	154.8 ± 28.6 minutes
Estimated blood loss	Mean ± SD	420 ± 135 ml
Hospital stays	Mean ± SD	6.4 ± 1.8 days
Drain removal	Within 48 hours	31 (77.5%)
Mobilization	Within 48 hours	34 (85.0%)
Blood transfusion	Required	10 (25.0%)
Type of surgery	Single-level PLIF	37 (92.5%)
	Two-level PLIF	3 (7.5%)

Table IV shows the functional outcome before and after PLIF. Significant improvements in VAS back pain (7.8 to 2.1), VAS leg pain (7.2 to 1.9), and ODI

score (58.4 to 22.6) were statistically significant at 6 months postoperative (p<0.001 for all). By 6 months, 85% and 80% of patients had improved walking

distance and daily activity, respectively, indicating progressive functional recovery and a significant decrease in pain-related disability following PLIF.

Table IV
Functional Outcome Before and After PLIF.

Variable	Category	Preoperative	3 Months	6 Months	p-value
VAS back pain score	Mean ± SD	7.8 ± 1.1	3.2 ± 1.0	2.1 ± 0.8	<0.001
VAS leg pain score	Mean ± SD	7.2 ± 1.3	2.8 ± 1.1	1.9 ± 0.9	<0.001
ODI score	Mean ± SD	58.4 ± 10.6	31.7 ± 8.9	22.6 ± 7.4	<0.001
Walking distance	Improved / n (%)	-	29 (72.5%)	34 (85.0%)	-
Daily activity	Returned/improved / n (%)	-	24 (60.0%)	32 (80.0%)	-

Figure 2 Radiological Outcome at Follow-up of the study population.

Figure 2 shows the radiological results at 6-month follow-up. Good implant positioning was noted in 95% of patients. The height of the disc was restored in 87.5%, and lumbar lordosis improved in 77.5%, which indicated successful spinal reconstruction. Definite fusion was obtained in 75% of patients, with probable fusion in an additional 20%, for an overall fusion rate of 95%. The incidence of implant-related

complications was low, with screw loosening being observed in only 2 patients (5%) and cage migration in 1 patient (2.5%).

Table V summarizes the total clinical outcomes and complications. A satisfactory outcome rate of 80% (excellent + good combined) was obtained with excellent results in 35% and good results in 45% of patients. The number of complications was

low and manageable; superficial wound infection and persistent radicular pain each occurred in 7.5% of cases, dural tear in 5%, and transient neurological deficit in 2.5%. Only 1 patient (2.5%) required reoperation. Notably, no perioperative mortality was observed, which confirms the overall safety of PLIF in this group of patients.

Table V

Overall Clinical Outcome and Complications of the study population.

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Overall outcome	Excellent	14	35.0%
	Good	18	45.0%
	Fair	6	15.0%
	Poor	2	5.0%
Satisfactory outcome	Excellent + good	32	80.0%
Complication	Superficial wound infection	3	7.5%
	Dural tear	2	5.0%
	Transient neurological deficit	1	2.5%
	Persistent radicular pain	3	7.5%
	Reoperation required	1	2.5%
Mortality	Death	0	0.0%

DISCUSSION

This prospective study demonstrated the functional and radiological outcomes of PLIF in 40 patients with degenerative lumbar spine disease in a tertiary care center in Bangladesh. The results show that pain, disability, and radiological parameters have significantly improved over a 6-month follow-up period, with a satisfactory complication profile and no mortality. The mean age of the study population was about 46.7 years, with a majority of the patients being male (55%) and rural dwellers (57.5%). 40% were engaged in manual labor, which is consistent with Fatima et al., who reported an established association between heavy occupational activity and degenerative lumbar disease [11]. The most frequent diagnosis was degenerative spondylolisthesis (45%), followed by

lumbar canal stenosis with instability (30%), in accordance with Weinstein et al. [12]. The average VAS back pain score decreased between 7.8 preoperatively and 2.1 at 6 months, and VAS leg pain improved between 7.2 and 1.9, both statistically significant (p<0.001). These results are consistent with those reported by Kim et al., who reported VAS improvements of similar magnitude following PLIF in degenerative spondylolisthesis [13]. The ODI score improved significantly from a preoperative mean of 58.4 (severe disability) to 22.6 at 6 months (moderate disability range), representing a clinically significant improvement well above the published minimum clinically important difference (MCID) of 12.8 points [14]. Similar ODI gains have been reported in several randomized and observational studies

evaluating outcomes after PLIF [15]. The radiological outcomes at 6 months were also favorable. In 75% of patients, definite fusion was achieved with probable fusion in an additional 20%, giving an overall fusion rate of 95%. This is in line with reported fusion rates of 85-97% as shown by Jitpakdee et al. [16]. The implant position was good in 95% of patients, and disc height restoration was observed in 87.5%, contributing to indirect neural decompression and biomechanical stability. Lumbar lordosis improved in 77.5% of patients, a significant parameter for global spinal alignment and long-term functional outcomes [17]. The overall satisfactory outcome rate (excellent + good) was 80%, which is similar to the results of similar studies in the region. In similar patient groups, Adogwa et al. reported satisfactory

rates of 76%-84% following lumbar interbody fusion procedures [18]. The most commonly operated level was L4-L5 (62.5%), consistent with Shim et al., who showed that this is the most biomechanically stressed level in the lumbar spine and the most frequent site of degenerative pathology [19]. The rate of complications in this study was within acceptable levels. Infection of the superficial wound was found in 7.5% of patients, which can be explained by the high prevalence of diabetes (22.5%) and smoking (32.5%), which are known risk factors of postoperative wound healing impairment [20]. Dural tear was observed in 5% of cases, which is in line with Desai et al., who reported rates of 3-9% in open lumbar spine surgery [21]. One patient had a transient neurological deficit that resolved fully, and only one patient needed reoperation. There were no perioperative deaths, highlighting the safety of PLIF when performed in well-equipped tertiary centers with experienced surgical teams [22]. The persistence of radicular pain in 7.5% of patients may be due to incomplete neural decompression, epidural fibrosis, or ongoing neuropathic pain that requires further multimodal treatment [23]. The results of this study support the use of PLIF as an effective surgical intervention for the treatment of degenerative lumbar spine disease and provide valuable, locally relevant data for a Bangladeshi patient population that is largely underrepresented in the global surgical literature.

LIMITATIONS

The study is also limited by its relatively small sample size (n = 40) from a single tertiary center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to larger patient populations. Also, the short 6-month follow-up period does not allow assessment of long-term outcomes, including adjacent segment degeneration, late hardware failure, and durable fusion consolidation.

CONCLUSION

Posterior lumbar interbody fusion is a safe, effective, and reproducible surgical technique for the management of degenerative lumbar spine disease. This study shows statistically and clinically significant changes in back and leg pain and functional disability at 6 months postoperatively. The radiological results, such as high fusion rates and satisfactory implant positioning, further confirm the effectiveness of PLIF in restoring lumbar stability. An overall satisfactory clinical outcome was achieved in 80% of patients, with a low complication rate and no perioperative mortality. These results confirm that PLIF can be done with good outcomes in a well-resourced tertiary care environment in Bangladesh and justify its

further use as a first-line surgical procedure in carefully selected patients with degenerative lumbar pathology.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Future studies with larger, multicenter, prospective cohorts and longer follow-up periods of at least 2 years are needed to better define the long-term clinical and radiological outcomes of PLIF in Bangladesh.

FUNDING

No funding sources

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

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